

Advancing data sharing and reuse: Insights from a workshop at the *Researcher to Reader* conference

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Introduction

Research data are increasingly being recognised as critical scholarly outputs, for example by US Federal Agencies, including the National Institutes of Health (National Institutes of Health, 2023). However, there are still issues with workflows and researcher incentives, and with aligning efforts to improve quality, reusability and user experiences (Alperin et al., 2022). To take stock on the current landscape for data sharing and open data use, and explore what lies ahead

toward further adoption of open data practices, we hosted a workshop at the [Researcher to Reader conference](#) in February 2024.

The goal was to bring together diverse perspectives and expertise to explore tangible next steps to drive further adoption of open data access and reuse. Importantly, the key stakeholders at the heart of this rapidly-developing space – the researchers themselves – are, for various reasons, often absent from ongoing efforts to improve the situation. Consequently, the co-facilitators for this workshop, Maria Guerreiro, Fiona Murphy and Iratxe Puebla, designed a programme agenda that provided researchers space to bring insights from their experiences of sharing research data, while also drawing on the expertise of the participating group of publishers, librarians and research ecosystem vendors. We invited two practising researchers to speak on a set of prepared topics, and interspersed the whole-group presentations with breakout discussions and report-back sessions. This white paper summarises the discussions at the workshop and aims to seed further conversations and progress in this space.

In recognition of the *Researcher to Reader* ethos, the whole workshop programme was deliberately constructed as an interactive arc spanning three sessions, starting with developing use cases for data sharing and reuse from the perspective of various stakeholders in the research community, going on to focus on the barriers to share and reuse data, and finally brainstorming what could be done to address those barriers.

The workshop attendees were typical of the *Researcher to Reader* demographic, consisting of publishers, vendors, and consultants, together with the two invited researchers.

Data sharing and reuse in the data lifecycle

In the initial session of the workshop, we aimed to develop a shared understanding among attendees about the motivations for data sharing, the stages of the data lifecycle, and when data may be shared and reused, and by whom.

To feed the discussion, we first heard the perspectives of two researchers: [Shozeb Haider](#), Professor of Computational Biophysics at University College London, and [Mauricio Contreras](#), Postdoctoral Scientist in plant immunology at The Sainsbury's Lab. Both noted that data sharing is an important practice as part of their research, and highlighted that making their data available enables reproducibility and accountability. While they acknowledged that some data must remain confidential for privacy or commercial reasons, they also highlighted that it is possible to put steps and safeguards in place to responsibly share data. The researchers noted that data sharing is often a requirement by funders and for journal publication, and in some communities, also an expectation per disciplinary norms. They viewed data sharing as integral to addressing concerns about research reproducibility and advancing knowledge and research efficiency.

We then asked attendees to break into three groups and reflect on the steps of the **research process where data can be shared and reused by different stakeholders** (i.e researchers,

funders, institutions, publishers etc). We provided a diagram outlining the data lifecycle from idea generation all the way down to research assessment, and asked participants to place examples of data sharing and reuse at the relevant locations in the data lifecycle.

In the larger group discussion that followed, some of the main themes that arose included:

- Data management plans (DMPs), and in particular, additional **support for developing DMPs**, to help researchers navigate the process effectively and in alignment with data policies.
- **Access to data** as a key research output to enable research collaboration. The importance of **metadata and contextual information** was highlighted in order to support reproducibility and/or effective data reuse to advance knowledge and promote research efficiency.
- The need for better ways to handle **data citations**, and to **connect data with figures, articles, and other outputs** to facilitate proper and meaningful **attribution and credit** for data contributions. A holistic view of scientific contributions, making information about data produced available to researchers but also funders is also critical to ensuring appropriate recognition for data outputs.
- The **role of data sharing (aligned with journal guidelines) in promoting research integrity and trust in research**.

Figure 1. Workshop participants identified at which stages of the research lifecycle data is being shared and reused by different stakeholders.

Based on the barriers identified in the second session, we assigned smaller groups to one of the three themes below and asked them to discuss potential solutions, considering which stakeholder(s) would need to lead or be involved:

1. Lack of credit and fear of scooping
2. Need for community best practices
3. Lack of support

We then had a larger group discussion about the solutions suggested, during which we also categorised the perceived effort versus value or impact for each proposed solution.

Figure 3. Miro board representation of the proposed solutions for the three key barriers for data sharing and reuse identified by the workshop participants, mapped against a Value-Effort matrix.

Findings

Potential solutions for barrier 1: Lack of credit and fear of scooping

The group sentiment was that lack of credit for sharing (and reusing) data remains deeply embedded within the research evaluation system and that therefore key stakeholders such as funders, institutions and publishers need to have clearer and more interconnected systems and metrics that enable recognition for data sharing and reuse practices. For instance, better

linkages between data and related research outputs, and the transfer of that information to the systems used by funders, institutions and publishers will be critical to measure the impact of open data, and map how data drives scientific advances. Infrastructure to enable publishers and repositories to deposit metadata relevant to datasets is already available through Crossref and DataCite, enabled through use of the Scholix schema. However, implementation of these workflows remains a challenge, for example among publishers. Further work is needed to encourage publishers to support these efforts; a recent relevant example is the [joint statement by STM, Crossref and DataCite](#) calling for adoption of best practices for research data sharing.

Another critical component is to make it possible for researchers to share and reuse data easily and at no additional direct expense to them. Support from funders and institutions towards the costs of publishing, archiving and preserving data via appropriate repositories and relevant associated infrastructure was considered fundamental to enable data sharing and data reuse.

In the context of concerns around data ownership, it is important to pursue education around the options available to share data – in which repository, using which licence, options available if access control is necessary. Funders, institutions and publishers should continue work towards aligning on a set of universal and general values – such as the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2023) – in order to standardise what is expected of researchers. Knowing what to expect when submitting a new grant, and getting familiarised with best practices to share data responsibly, can mitigate any preconceived apprehension researchers may hold around data sharing.

Potential solutions for barrier 2: Need for community best practices

A common theme was that the specific needs of individual scientific communities should be considered, but that it is also critical to have a set of universal applicable standards that communities can easily and consistently follow regardless. Like in the previous group, the FAIR principles were highlighted as the kind of general principles that can and should be applied.

When we talk about communities, we often do so in the context of disciplinary communities. This group highlighted that scholarly societies can leverage the strong ties they have with their members to convene discussions about best practices, ensuring that any policies developed are aligned with – and will have the support of – their communities. An interesting note was that communities may also mean regional or national groups, who need to comply with different governmental or institutional policies and practices; those specificities also need to be considered, for instance, to prevent any data-sharing requirements by publishers conflicting with local or national data policies. Organisations like the [Research Data Alliance](#) can promote general and standardised processes and principles through dialogue (e.g., working groups) or through the publication of case studies that are context specific. This kind of multi-stakeholder organisation can also play a role in collecting and distributing existing resources, to avoid duplication of efforts where similar applicable guidelines or documentation is already available. Learned societies were also encouraged to integrate these community efforts.

Potential solutions for barrier 3: Lack of support

The group highlighted that often researchers are left to navigate the data-sharing landscape by themselves. The discussion touched on the need for training in data management and for the existence of data stewards, who are knowledgeable in the solutions available to manage and share different kinds of data (including datasets that involve privacy or legal considerations) and provide valuable advice to researchers. Many institutions have their own institutional repository or partner with a third-party data repository, and the group suggested that researchers should be involved in the decision-making process if a new data sharing and archiving solution is being implemented at the institutional level.

It is fair to say that other stakeholders in the research ecosystem, beyond researchers themselves, also lack support. Improvements to technology could facilitate better interoperability across systems, and a better use and combination of resources could help alleviate the administrative and legal burden for publishers, institutions and funders.

Recommendations

The discussion at the workshop made it clear that there is strong support for data sharing across stakeholders, with a shared vision of why this practice should be supported in order to advance research efforts, reinforce integrity, and ensure inclusive evaluation of research contributions. At the same time, it is also clear that data sharing is not yet the norm across all communities and that barriers remain to the adoption of data sharing and reuse. While the discussion touched on some areas that are specific to certain communities, there were also several clear themes applicable across research communities and research-supporting stakeholders, which if addressed could broaden and accelerate adoption of data-sharing practices.

The categorization of the proposed solutions reflects, to a certain degree, the level of maturity of specific areas that support open data. The group saw two areas as having potential for significant impact but requiring lower effort. The first related to the infrastructure for data sharing and reuse, as well as that required for collecting data metrics and relational metadata between datasets and other outputs. The second related to support for researchers e.g., via training and dedicated roles that support data management and stewardship. Both of these areas have seen substantial progress in the last decade. A wide range of repositories is now available, including a diversity of features such as curation, embargo options or controlled access ([re3data](#) provides a registry of research data repositories). [DataCite](#) provides DOIs for datasets and services to connect datasets to other objects and identifiers (e.g., Scholix schema, ORCID, ROR). DataCite also provides services to report and access data usage counts, and the [Make Data Count](#) initiative has developed guidance and processes to consistently report measures of data usage. With regard to support for researchers, a number of institutions have created data steward roles to provide training and support for researchers on many areas of data sharing, including data management plans, choice of repository, and more. A number of funders now include dedicated funds for data management as part of their grants.

With regard to the areas of high impact but which will also require high effort, two main topics arose. The first relates to incentives for data sharing and data reuse, that is, the need to recognize those activities in research assessment processes, as this will influence researcher behaviour and drive culture change. While many funders and organisations have mandates for data sharing, most research evaluation processes still do not regard data as a primary research contribution. The second is the need for greater consistency on standards and community expectations for data sharing. The research ecosystem needs to account for the wide range of data types created in research activities, and also the fact that different communities create and consume data to different degrees. This has resulted in a complex ecosystem which can be tricky to navigate for those who are new to it, or lacking time or resources. How do we reconcile the need to be attentive to discipline-specific needs while making it simpler for the broader community to adopt best practices in open data?

Drawing on the discussions at the workshop, we outline below a few recommendations for how different stakeholders can drive forward data sharing and reuse:

Recommended actions	Examples
FUNDERS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Require data management plans and provide information on what is expected in these ● Encourage researchers to deposit datasets at repositories that assign PIDs ● Encourage researchers to cite datasets they have used – their own and others’ – in their research outputs ● Ask researchers to report the datasets they shared and their reuse in grant applications and reports ● Ensure that data contributions are considered as part of the grant application review, by having a dedicated review of data outputs, including data expertise in review panels 	<p>ASAP’s Open Access Policy</p> <p>NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy</p> <p>Horizon 2020 Data Management Guidance</p> <p>Supporting the Implementation of the 2023 NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy: What is Still Needed</p>
INSTITUTIONS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Have designated data stewards, who can provide training and support for researchers across different groups and departments ● Support initiatives to incorporate open science practices, including open data, in research assessment ● Ask researchers to report the datasets they shared and their reuse in job applications, tenure and promotion packets 	<p>TU Delft Data Stewardship programme</p> <p>OpenAire RDM Task Force</p> <p>EMBL guidelines for research assessment (which mention data)</p> <p>Puebla <i>et al.</i>, Ten simple rules for recognizing data and software contributions in hiring, promotion,</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensure a dedicated review of data contributions as part of tenure and promotion, including clear guidelines and dedicated reviewers with expertise in data ● Participate in the development of metrics which support assessment of the value and impact of datasets 	<p>and tenure</p> <p>Coalitions for reforming research assessment: CoARA, HELIOS Open</p>
REPOSITORIES	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implement open metadata and PIDs to enable interoperability with systems and platforms used by other stakeholders (e.g., used for research evaluation) ● Support contextual information to accompany the data to promote interpretability and reuse (e.g., a README file) ● Foster adherence to a universal set of principles for data stewardship (e.g., FAIR) ● Implement processes that support the long-term preservation of datasets ● Engage in dialogue with specific disciplinary and regional communities (e.g., via scholarly societies) ● Implement processes to enable visibility and assessment of the usage of published datasets (e.g., data citations and usage metrics) ● Collaborate with other data repositories to streamline the data sharing and reuse experience for researchers 	<p>FAIR principles</p> <p>Dryad's best practices for creating reusable data publications</p> <p>NIH Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative</p> <p>Dataverse documentation to enable the set up of the Make Data Count metrics in data repositories</p> <p>Make Data Count recommendations, including the COUNTER Code of Practice for Research Data for normalised reports of data usage</p>
PUBLISHERS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaborate with other stakeholders and contribute to developing standard workflows and guidelines for authors ● Develop and implement journal data policies, in consultation with individual editorial boards (to ensure each policy is domain-appropriate), then regularly review and update journal instructions for authors ● Provide clear guidance on Data Availability Statements, with examples authors can easily utilise, and ensure these statements are machine-readable ● Articulate guidelines for data citation for authors, reviewers and editors ● Work with vendors to ensure metadata for data citations is preserved throughout the production process and deposited with Crossref 	<p>Cousijn <i>et al.</i>, A data citation roadmap for scientific publishers</p> <p>Updates to eLife's data sharing policies</p> <p>Springer Nature's Data Availability Statements guidance</p> <p>Muench A., The Roles of Data Editors in Astronomy</p> <p>Best Practices in Research Data Sharing - STM (stm-assoc.org)</p>
SCHOLARLY SOCIETIES (may also be publishers, in which case see above)	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify and/or develop domain specific, practicable standards for data collection and management ● Consider instigating data re-use and data rescue programmes or prizes to showcase what value data can provide to the field ● Work with community leaders who have an interest in data sharing and reuse to demonstrate high-status behaviour ● Encourage data sharing/reuse streams at key conferences, and articles and special issues in key domain publications ● Promote data sharing and reuse educational sessions and resources 	<p>FASEB DataWorks! (provides data prizes, educational webinars and helpdesk support)</p> <p>Research Parasites awards for rigorous secondary data analysis</p> <p>AGU Data Leadership programme</p> <p>Special Issue: Secondary analysis of large quantitative datasets</p>
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Table 1. Recommended actions that stakeholders in the research lifecycle can take to promote wider data sharing and reuse practices.

We recognize that the different recommendations above vary in the time and resources required for their implementation, and also that different stakeholders and groups may be at different levels of maturity in adopting some of the steps outlined. We encourage the different groups to identify one item among those outlined that they are confident they can move forward within their communities, institutions or networks, and to pursue its implementation.

Researchers’ perspective: an additional validation step

In May 2024, Fiona Murphy conducted a webinar about this workshop with [Leeds ReproducibiliTea](#), an early-career researcher focused journal club based at the University of Leeds. This group promotes discussions on improving openness and integrity in research practices across several disciplines.

The participants were walked through the methodology and findings of the workshop at the *Researcher to Reader* conference, and undertook a series of validation exercises via an online whiteboard. Firstly, they were asked to critique a digitised version of Figure 3. They broadly agreed with the workshop prioritisation grid, adding a few additional suggested interventions, including ‘Example datasets to validate open source software’ (high impact/low effort) and ‘Research-field specific advice on what to think about when identifying what data to share’ (high impact/high effort). Secondly, they grouped the interventions on a prioritisation thermometer (hot = high priority). Finally, the six highest priority interventions were identified, and participants were invited to populate a grid with information about what initiatives are already in existence, what can be done at the individual/institutional level, and what is currently preventing progress.

Figure 4: Leeds ReproducibiliTea participants' suggestions for high priority interventions and opportunities for action.

Priorities included: publishers to employ journal data editors; providing researchers with strong evidence of data-sharing impact i.e., the benefits of data sharing; funders to provide clearer data policies; repositories to collect and share metrics for data; communities to develop data standards; and for *someone* to develop 'straightforward data deposit workflows'. Although this does seem to suggest that researchers and research managers were primarily looking to the other stakeholders to improve support and practices – which makes sense given that funders, publishers and repositories provide the funding, hosting, and infrastructures for scholarly communications – there were also some potential actions that could sit within the research communities, such as 'encouraging learned societies to work with institutions to deliver open research training', and 'concentrating efforts on post-graduates and sharing data in the context of thesis publication'. The need to build 'researcher skills, especially on modern methods for de-identification like synthetic datasets' was also highlighted. The group discussed the fact that even when institutions make considerable efforts to support the adoption of best practices, researchers working at the grassroots level (postgraduates and postdocs) may be unaware or are slow to implement them; it is thus relevant to better understand the reasons for this particular blockage in the system.

Obtaining researchers' insight on the workshop's findings was encouraging insofar as their respective contributions largely aligned. However, this additional step also reinforced our original assumption about the considerable challenge involved in including researchers in these sorts of debates. This is something that should be continually addressed in order to build feedback loops where interventions can be introduced, implemented, and further developed by all parties.

Achieving full adoption of data-sharing practices, and the recognition of open data and data reuse as a primary part of the research ecosystem, will require multiple steps and regular refinement of practices and policies. However, all stakeholders have the capacity and the responsibility to support progress towards this goal, starting now.

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Competing interests

Iratxe Puebla is Director of Make Data Count, an initiative that drives development and adoption of open data metrics, and an employee of DataCite, which provides services to create and manage DOIs and associated metadata for datasets and open research outputs.

Maria Guerreiro is Head of Partnership Development at Dryad, an open data publishing platform and a community committed to the open availability and routine re-use of research data.

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Disclosures

The summary of notes from the discussion at the different workshop sessions (in sections 'Data sharing and reuse in the data lifecycle', 'Barriers to data sharing and reuse') was aided by ChatGPT. The authors reviewed and edited the summary for accuracy and clarity.

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